

THE ROLE OF ART AND CULTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF RENEWED UZBEKISTAN

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Yangilanayotgan O'zbekistonda san'at va madaniyatning rivojlanishi va uning janiyat taraqqiyotidagi muhim strategik ahamiyati haqida fikr va mulohazalar bayon etilgan. Shuningdek, inson tarbiyasi, uning ma'naviy va estetik qarashlarining shakllanishida mazkur faoliyatning funksiyalari haqida ham yetarlicha ma'lumotlar berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Yangilanayotgan O'zbekiston, taraqqiyot, san'at, madaniyat, vatanarvarlik, madaniy meros, kasbiy madaniy yuksalish, zamonaviy o'zgarishlar.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье представлены мнения и мысли о развитии искусства и культуры в Узбекистане и его важной стратегической роли в развитии общества. Также достаточно сведений о функциях этой деятельности в формировании воспитания человека, его духовно-эстетических взглядов.*

Ключевые слова: *Обновляющийся Узбекистан, развитие, развитие, искусство, культура, патриотизм, культурное наследие, профессиональное культурное развитие, современные изменения.*

Annotation: *This article discusses the development of art and culture in Uzbekistan and its important strategic role in the development of the world. There is also enough information about the functions of human activity, the formation of his spiritual and aesthetic views.*

Key words: *Renewing Uzbekistan, development, development, art, culture, patriotism, cultural heritage, professional cultural development, modern changes.*

In recent years, the further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the creation of a new history of Uzbekistan, the preservation and promotion of tangible and intangible cultural heritage, the further popularization of folklore and amateur art, Systematic measures

have been taken to ensure active integration into the space, innovative development of culture and arts. In particular, the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan was approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4038 dated November 28, 2018, and a number of projects were implemented to ensure the implementation of this decision.

In particular, the International Conference of Maqom Art, the International Festival of Bakhshi, the Sharq Taronalari International Music Festival, the Great Silk Road International Folk Art Festival and the Dance Festival. The international festival "Magic" has been organized, and an effective system for further development of unique examples and traditions of Uzbek classical and folk art, as well as cultural dialogue has been established.

At the same time, the introduction of modern information and communication technologies in the field, training of highly qualified personnel, search and support of talented young artists, music textbooks, and music collections and teaching materials for educational institutions an integrated system of supply has been created. In particular, to increase the level of cultural and recreational services for citizens living in remote areas, the activities of theaters, museums, mobile circuses and zoos in all regions of the country are constantly being organized. In addition, the program of additional measures to accelerate the reforms in the field of culture and arts, further improve the activities of cultural bodies and institutions, the further development of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the concept of further development of national culture in Uzbekistan.

In order to ensure the implementation of targets for 2021-2025: licensing of various concert performances, the establishment of the Chamber of Copyright of Artists, Creators and Performers of Culture and Arts, 2020 From September 1, a number of similar projects will be implemented in the system of state bodies and organizations, including the introduction of a 50% discount on rent for concert programs, full-time concert programs in palaces of culture and other institutions.

It is known that within the framework of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the country in 2017-2021, about 300 laws aimed at radical reform of all spheres of state and public life, more than 4,000 Presidents of the Republic of Uzbekistan decisions were made. Because of the last five years of reforms, the necessary political, legal, socio-economic and scientific-educational foundations for the

construction of a new Uzbekistan have been created in our country. The State Program of Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, consisting of priority areas, has been approved.

We all know that the role and influence of culture and art in the unification and development of society, the glorification of the people and the Motherland in the world is invaluable, instilling in the human heart noble qualities and noble feelings. If we look at the history of our country, we see that such unique events as the First and Second Renaissances were first nourished by our ancient and rich culture and formed because of our immortal values and traditions. Today, our people are well aware of the fact that hard-working and dedicated representatives of culture and art, creative intellectuals are emerging as a decisive force in shaping the image of New Uzbekistan, the great goal we have set for ourselves - the foundation of the Third Renaissance. Appreciates.

In this regard, it should be noted that in recent years, a number of laws, decrees and decisions have been adopted and a lot of work is being done to develop the industry. In particular, in accordance with the Concept of Further Development of National Culture and the Presidential Decree "On Additional Measures for the Further Development of Culture and Arts", a new strategy of reforms in this area is being adopted and gradually implemented. First, the Ministry of Culture was reorganized in accordance with modern requirements, its central and regional structures, the activities of various creative organizations and associations were improved. Unique forms of our national art have been restored, dozens of new cultural and art institutions have been established, and about 15 theaters, museums and reserves have been established.

In particular, the State Philharmonic of Uzbekistan, the Centers of National Maqom and Bakhshi Art, exemplary Maqom and Bakhshi ensembles in the regions, the Union of Theater and Cinema Workers, the State Dance Ensemble "Spring" are working effectively. In the recent past, the Uzbek National Institute of Musical Arts named after Yunus Rajabi, the National Institute of Pop Art named after Botir Zokirov, the Urgench branch of the Uzbek State Academy of Choreography, the Republican College of Music and Arts and the Nukus School of Opera and Ballet was established. The regular holding of international festivals of makom and baxshi arts and crafts in our country serves to promote our national culture in the world. As a result, the ancient and unique art of our people is gaining high recognition of the world community.

This is evidenced by the fact that “Khorezm Lezgis” and the art of baxshi are included in the UNESCO Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. Much is being done to encourage the hard work of employees in the field, to increase their role and prestige in society. In particular, the fact that April 15 is the Day of Culture and Arts in our country is a new step in this direction. Our lofty goals and achievements set out in the New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan set important tasks for us in all areas, including culture and the arts. First, to further enhance the principles of nationalism in our national culture and art, to turn it into an area that truly expresses the heart and soul of our country, meets the highest international standards and requirements, the population, first, our growing children. We rely on thousands of dedicated representatives of culture and art like you to protect the environment from destructive ideas, spiritual threats, peace and stability, mutual respect and solidarity in our society.

In this regard, we all understand the role and influence of our theaters, which our great-enlightened ancestor Mahmudhoja Behbudi described as a "model". In December last year, the President issued a decree on the further development of opera and ballet in the country, which identified the necessary measures in this regard. In addition, state grants for the best projects will be allocated from this year to support students of universities of culture and arts, non-governmental theater studios, and encourage their aspirations. Assistance to graduates of fine and applied arts and design, as well as artists engaged in freelance work, including the provision of creative workshops, "teacher-student" A number of measures are also planned to strengthen mothers. In short, the support of cultural and art organizations, in particular, the multinational creative and technical communities working in the cultural centers of the regions, encouraging the creation of high works of art, their sincere service to our country The work to create the necessary conditions for.

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